

CHARACTERISING THE INTER-PLY BEHAVIOUR OF NON-CRIMP FABRICS DURING SINGLE DIAPHRAGM FORMING EXPERIMENT

Yilong Li¹, Guy Lawrence², Lee Harper³ and Michael Sutcliffe⁴

¹Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge
Engineering Dept, Trumpington St, CB2 1PZ, Cambridge, UK
Email: y1895@cam.ac.uk, web page: <https://www.cam.ac.uk/>

²Composites Research Group, University of Nottingham
Advanced manufacturing Building, Jubilee Campus, NG7 2GW, Nottingham, UK
Email: guydlawrence@gmail.com, web page: <https://www.nottingham.ac.uk/>

³Composites Research Group, University of Nottingham
Advanced manufacturing Building, Jubilee Campus, NG7 2GW, Nottingham, UK
Email: lee.harper@nottingham.ac.uk, web page: <https://www.nottingham.ac.uk/>

⁴Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge
Engineering Dept, Trumpington St, CB2 1PZ, Cambridge, UK
Email: mpfs@eng.cam.ac.uk, web page: <https://www.cam.ac.uk/>

Keywords: Fabrics, Preform, RTM, Process monitoring, FEA

ABSTRACT

The Single Diaphragm Forming (SDF) process has received limited attention in the literature compared with the Double Diaphragm Forming (DDF). However, its advantages in multi-layer preforming have led to its adoption in certain manufacturing contexts. To facilitate a more comprehensive investigation of the SDF process, a compact experimental rig capable with various tool geometries was designed and constructed. Previous research has highlighted the critical influence of friction between fabric plies in forming defects during the preforming of multi-ply diaphragms. Inter-fabric sliding has been introduced as an additional quantitative metric to establish a connection between interface friction and preforming quality to enable more effective monitoring of fabric behaviour during preforming. In the SDF experiments, the opacity of both the diaphragm and fabric poses a significant challenge to direct visual tracking of the lower fabric plies using photographic or videographic methods. Consequently, an indirect measurement technique has been developed by applying pre-painted grease dots to the fabric surface and subsequently tracking their deformed configurations post-forming. This methodology has been implemented across a range of tool geometries within the SDF experiments. By comparing the experimental sliding data with results obtained from finite element (FE) simulations, the sliding metric provides valuable insights into the dynamics between fabric layers and an evaluation of the current simulation models in terms of fabric interface behaviour. Future work will focus on employing this integrated approach to further investigate the correlation between friction, inter-ply sliding and preforming defects, and on extending the sliding tracking methodology to the study of the DDF process.

1 INTRODUCTION

Diaphragm forming is an open-moulding preforming technique developed for shaping dry textile reinforcements into complex geometries before resin infusion in liquid composite moulding (LCM) processes. Compared to conventional closed-moulding or draping methods, the diaphragm forming process offers a balance between efficiency and preforming quality [1]. Owing to its compatibility with automation and scalability, the diaphragm forming process is increasingly adopted in high-rate manufacturing sectors such as aerospace and automotive, where geometric complexity and production efficiency are critical requirements. Based on the number of diaphragms involved in each manufacture,

the diaphragm forming process can be further classified into single diaphragm forming (SDF) and double diaphragm forming (DDF). By slightly compromising processing stability, the SDF reduces the complexity of the manufacturing rig and material requirements compared to the DDF. Moreover, the SDF process allows for sequentially preforming operations, thereby enabling the manufacturing of thicker fabric structures [2].

Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) is a class of dry fibre reinforcements used extensively in the manufacture of high-performance composite materials. Unlike traditional woven fabrics, in which yarns are interlaced, NCF is composed of multiple layers of unidirectional (UD) fibres that are stitched or bound together without any crimping, which achieves better mechanical performance in the final products [3]. NCF materials can be classified in various ways, allowing for more precise descriptions based on the orientation of the UD layers, the number of plies, or the style of interlayer connection.

Numerous experimental setups have been designed and fabricated to investigate the processing mechanisms of preforming and to optimise both the procedure and product quality. Viisainen et al. [4] explained the mechanism of wrinkle generation through the draping experiments with the aid of digital image correlation (DIC) technology. Lawrence et al. [5] explored the contact situation of fabric samples under high compaction force, as well as the effect of the variability of vacuum pressure with the micro-CT devices. Yu et al. [6] discussed the effect of inter-ply sliding during multi-ply DDF under both lubricated and unlubricated conditions. Meanwhile, the finite element (FE) method has been widely applied to simulate the preforming process from both meso-level and macro-level [7-9].

This study proposes a novel design for an SDF experimental rig, upon which a new experimental methodology is developed. The method exploits the fluidity of grease on the fabric surface to monitor interply sliding between the fabric sample during the SDF process by measuring the deformation of pre-applied grease marks. A selection of experimental results derived from the proposed rig and methodology is also presented to demonstrate the applicability and effectiveness of the approach.

2 SINGLE DIAPHRAGM FORMING EXPERIMENT RIG

The SDF process, as one form of diaphragm forming, offers methodological advantages such as a simpler structure and more convenient operation compared with the DDF process. Though with higher variability, the SDF experiments can comprehensively represent the behaviour of the fabric and diaphragm under vacuum force in the DDF process. Therefore, a lab-level SDF rig has been designed and assembled to achieve rapid experiment methodology validation and simulation model validation at a lower cost.

The SDF experiment rig is designed for dry fabric preforming only, without the involvement of resin injection and heating systems. The schematic of the SDF experiment process is shown in Figure 1. By generating a vacuum between the diaphragm and rig base, the flat fabric plies are formed into 3D structures by vacuum pressure. The edge of the diaphragm is sealed against the edge of the rig base to form an enclosed chamber, after which air is evacuated from the system.

Figure 1: The scheme for the SDF process: a) Material preparation and diaphragm boundary clamping, and b) Vacuum forming

2.1 Materials

The target material in the SDF process is a biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF fabric with pillar stitch manufactured by Hexcel under the name ‘HiMaxTM CGL4790 - FCIM359 NCF’. The mechanical property of this material has been previously characterised through a standard picture frame test, while a shell-membrane element has been created and validated for the simulation of the NCF with the FE method [10]. The tribological properties of the NCF have been measured using the lap shear friction test developed by Lawrence et al. [5].

The StretchLon[®] HT-350, a high-elongation vacuum film with an elongation at break of 550% and a temperature resistance of up to 162 °C, was selected as the diaphragm material for the experiments. This vacuum film shows good ductility during stretching, which allows more deformation and maintains good vacuum integrity during the SDF process [11]. BR180 is a 140 gsm non-woven polyester felt fabric used as a breather layer during the vacuum forming of fabric laminates, which avoids the formation of bubbles and ensures the uniform application of vacuum force. Other materials and components applied in the diaphragm forming rig and experiment design are listed in Table 1.

Description	Manufacturer	Type	Reusability
Biaxial NCF	Hexcel [®]	HiMax TM FCIM359	No
Vacuum Diaphragm	Tygavac Ltd UK	StretchLon [®] HT-350	No
Lithium Grease	MG Chemicals	No. 8461 Lithium Grease	No
Breather	AeroFilm [®]	BR180 Breather Cloth	Yes
Vacuum Pump	DVP Vacuum Tech	VP-EC4-UK	Yes
Vacuum Gauge	Vac Checker [®]	VE-VCG	Yes

Table 1: The components and materials used in the single diaphragm forming rig and experiment.

2.2 The Design of the Single Diaphragm Rig

The rig contains four main components: base, blank holder, detachable tool, and vacuum system with pressure gauge, as shown in Figure 2 a). The vacuum port is located on the side of the rig base and is connected to the pressure gauge through tubes. The digital vacuum gauge connecting the rig inlet and the gauge delivers reliable pressure measurements in the range of 1100 to 0.00 mbar and with a resolution of 0.01 mbar. The base is fixed to the experiment table with screws to avoid instability during experiments. The base is assembled with three parts: a top board with ventholes, a middle frame and a bottom board. The vacuum port is placed on the middle frame, while these components are assembled through screws near the edge and sealed with the vacuum tape and the multi-purpose sealant.

To ensure a uniform vacuum pressure, 72 ventholes with a 10 mm diameter are evenly drilled on the top baseboard except for the tool region, as shown in Figure 2 b). Breathers are laid between the tool edge and the ventholes to avoid air cavities near the junction between the tool and the rig base. The sealing strips are added between the bed and the blank holder. Under the clamp force from the blank holder, the strips deform elastically to secure good sealing during the preforming.

Figure 2: a) Assembly of SDF rig system with fabric samples, b) the structure of the top base board

3 THE INTER-PLY SLIDING TRACKING METHODOLOGY

In previous research, various parameters and methodologies have been introduced to monitor and understand the behaviour of fabrics during the preforming process as detailed in the introduction. One area of research focuses on dynamically tracking the visible surfaces with videos or photos to explain the correlation between deformation and defect. Other research topic concentrates on statistically analysing the preforming results with various methods. For example, digital image correlation and micro-CT scanning are widely used for dynamic and static research, respectively. However, both processes are not sufficient to dynamically monitor the fabric behaviour in the multi-ply forming. Therefore, a novel methodology is proposed for the indirect measurement of interply sliding between fabrics by tracking the changes in marker points, which helps build a bridge between the manufacturing setup and the preform quality.

3.1 Methodology Introduction

In industrial production, grease is used to label the surface of carbon fabrics, as it provides stable and long-lasting markings with good clarity. For a period following the painting process, the grease retains a certain degree of fluidity and viscosity. Consequently, when relative motion occurs between the two contacting surfaces, the shape of the grease undergoes deformation. This inspired an experimental methodology to track the interply sliding through the deformation of painted marks between the fabrics.

The method is presented in Figure 3. Before the experiments, the grease dots are placed on the fabric sheet as marks, which are sandwiched between the interested fabric interface in the experiment. During the diaphragm forming process, the fabric plies have relative motion, while the grease dots are flattened by the compaction of fabric sheets, accompanied by the sliding-induced shape elongation. By evaluating the final shape of the grease marks, the sliding distance on the marked position is indirectly measured.

Figure 3: Flowchart of the method for measuring relative inter-ply sliding based on grease marks.

To ensure the consistency of the grease dots applied during the experiments, a PVC board with precision-drilled holes was employed as a mould for dot placement. The thickness of the mould board is 1.6 mm, while the diameter of the holes is 4 mm. The painting process is shown in Figure 4. After filling the mould hole with grease, a flat blade is used to remove the excess grease on the top of the mould. Vertically lifting the mould, the grease dot is placed on the fabric surface with the shape of a 1.6 mm high cylinder because of the viscosity and surface tension.

3.2 Method Consistency

To validate the feasibility of the proposed method, two well-designed experiments were conducted. The first assessed the stability of the grease quantity of the grease dots, while the second evaluated the morphological stability of the grease dots under pure compaction.

The weight consistency test focuses on verifying whether the quantity of grease within the dots remains uniform, assuming their external shapes are geometrically ideal. The experimental result is

shown in Figure 5. The difference in the amount of grease within each dot is mainly induced by operational errors in the experimental procedures. Therefore, the external shape of the grease dots is first evaluated and classified into two groups: dots with an ideal external shape (ideal dot) and dots with defects (defect dot). The ideal dots have an ideal cylindrical shape, while the dots with obvious grease loss or other problems (asymmetric, non-circular, etc.) are marked as defective dots.

Figure 4: Fabric grease painting process with 4 mm plastic mould

The ideal dots are directly used in the experiments, while the defective dots are removed and repainted. By dot classification and replacement/discarding of defective dots, the grease weight consistency is improved. As shown in Figure 5, the coefficient of variation of the dot weight (ideal dots only) is reduced to 5.6%, which is acceptable for the following diaphragm forming experiments.

Figure 5: Grease weight consistency experiment result: a) Weight of every grease point, and b) statistical data for grease weight

The deformation of the grease shape is influenced not only by the original placement of the grease dots but also by the fabric interface properties, such as fabric direction and interface compaction force. To quantify these factors, an experiment for the grease marks with pure compaction is designed to quantify the mark shape with different fabric directions. In the experiments, the prepared fabric stacks have been sealed into a vacuum bag, while the bag is vacuumed to imitate the vacuum compaction in the diaphragm forming.

The mark shape after compaction is tracked through images, while the ideal shape of a grease dot under pure compaction was derived based on the averaged geometry of these shapes. As shown in Figure 6, the shape of the grease dots is influenced by the relative orientation of the fibre tows. In the 90° case, the grease tends to form a circular mark, while in the 45° and 90° cases, the grease shape is elongated towards the direction of the bisector of the acute angle between the tows. Among all fibre setups, the shape of the grease mark after pure compaction exhibited good stability across repeated experiments. This ensures that any subsequent changes in the grease mark morphology can be attributed solely to the sliding motion between fabric plies during the experiment, rather than to the inherent variability of the grease itself.

Figure 6: Standard no-sliding grease shape with \varnothing 4 mm mould under different tow directions

3.3 The Post-Processing of Experiment Results

In the post-processing, the shape of the grease marks is recorded through photography, as shown in Figure 7 a). The red points in the grease marks are the pre-drawn reference points to locate the original position of the mark. The reference points are painted with solvent-based markers, which dry out rapidly before the grease painting. The post-process involves mark boundary tracking and the sliding calculation. Subsequently, the boundary and initial mark centre are selected from the photos, as shown in Figure 7 b).

Figure 7: The image record and boundary track of the grease marks after diaphragm forming experiments.

The mark shape after sliding is similar to the trajectory of an elliptical dot translating on the plane, as shown in Figure 8 a). The selected original centre of the grease dot is marked as point B on the grease. The chord AC is the longest line segment on the figure that is intercepted by the line passing through point B. The length L1 is the sum of the grease elongation length and the radius of the no-slip mark shape in the sliding direction, while the length L2 is the radius of the no-slip mark shape in the opposite direction of sliding. As the no-slip shape is centre symmetry, the grease elongation length can be calculated as the difference between L1 and L2.

While the actual sliding distance and the measured elongation length of the grease were generally not equivalent across most experiments, a linear relationship was consistently observed between them. Based on a series of overlap tests performed at 1 bar pressure [5], the linear correlation between the two parameters is described by the following equation, as shown in Figure 8 b):

$$\text{Grease Elongation Length} = 0.85 \times \text{Sliding Distance} \quad (1)$$

Based on the aforementioned procedure and equation, the relative interply sliding at the grease dot position during the preforming can be derived.

Figure 8: a) Sliding calculation for tracked grease mark shape in the post-process. b) Correlation between grease elongation length and sliding distance

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To validate the effectiveness of the aforementioned method and to enhance understanding of the SDF process, a series of experiments were conducted using the previously described SDF rig, employing the grease technique to track the sliding of specific positions. The experimental results were compared with those from finite element (FE) simulations [11], enabling an analysis of the limitations inherent in the current experimental methods and simulation models.

Four different tool geometries are included in the experiments: a hemisphere tool, a double dome tool and two spar tools with different ramp angles [4]. The hemisphere tool and the double dome tool, known as the benchmark geometries, are widely used in the preforming research on woven and NCF fabrics. In addition to wrinkling, which is the primary focus of this study, bridging is another common defect encountered during preforming. Although the impact of bridging on the manufacturing process is less severe and it can typically be eliminated in subsequent processing steps, bridging still affects the fabric behaviour during processing and therefore needs to be taken into consideration. Among the experiments conducted with the four tools, bridging is expected to occur in the benchmark tools, whereas it does not appear in the experiments using the spar tools.

4.1 The Experiment Result with Different Tools

In the experiment with spar tools, 15 grease dots were applied at designated points, maintaining a minimum spacing of 2 cm between each to prevent mutual interference. A total of 12 dots were placed at the corners of the sample, two dots were positioned along the edges, and one dot was placed in the centre as a control, in Figure 9 a). The formed fabric samples are shown in Figure 9 b) and c).

Figure 9: The SDF experiments with the spar tools: a) the prepared fabric sample with grease dots, b) the formed fabric sample with the high ramp spar tool and c) the formed fabric sample with the low ramp spar tool.

The processed sliding distances from the grease method are compared with the FE simulation result, as shown in Figure 10. The comparison shown in the figure indicates that, in both the high ramp spar and low ramp spar experiments, the sliding directions of the tracked data points closely

correspond with the predicted directions. However, the predicted sliding distances are consistently larger than the distances observed in the experiments.

Figure 10: The sliding measurement result for the SDF experiments with the spar tools, where the sliding vectors are marked by arrows on the grease mark positions.

In the experiments with the benchmark tools, 17 grease dots were applied at designated points, maintaining a minimum spacing of 3 cm between each to prevent mutual interference. A total of 12 dots were placed at the corners of the sample, four dots were positioned along the edges, and one dot was placed in the centre as a control, as shown in Figure 11 a). The formed fabric samples are shown in Figure 11 b) and c).

Figure 11: The SDF experiments with the benchmark tools: a) the prepared fabric sample with grease dots, b) the formed fabric sample with the double dome tool, and c) the formed fabric sample with the hemisphere tool.

The processed sliding distances are compared with the FE simulation result, as shown in Figure 12 respectively. In the figure, the sliding vectors from the grease dots in the low sliding regions show certain differences from the simulation results in both direction and magnitude.

Figure 12: The sliding measurement result for the SDF experiments with the benchmark tools, where the sliding vectors are marked by arrows on the grease mark positions

In the high sliding regions (top-right and bottom-left corners), the experimental results show a good agreement with the prediction from the simulation results in the direction, while the sliding distances from the simulation are longer than those measured in the experiment, similar to the situation in the spar experiments. Overall, in the experiments conducted with the benchmark tool, the discrepancy between the experimental and simulation results was greater in both direction and magnitude.

4.2 Discussions

The application of the grease mark method in SDF experiments proved to be an effective means of tracking the sliding behaviour in specific regions. Adding additional grease dots has a negligible impact on the preforming result. A comparison between the experimental and simulation results reveals a good level of agreement in the prediction of relative sliding, particularly in regions where the sliding distance exceeds 8 mm. The current simulation model tends to overestimate the sliding distance during the SDF process, while the experimental method exhibits considerable uncertainty in capturing small-scale sliding displacements.

The error associated with the experimental methodology primarily arises from three sources. Firstly, the accuracy of sliding measurement relies on the intimate contact between the upper and lower surfaces. However, the relative opening between the fabric plies exists in the diaphragm forming process, especially for the SDF experiment, because of the lack of compaction. Secondly, the sliding trajectory is assumed to be linear, while tow twisting is ignored to reduce the complexity of the grease shape. This assumption may introduce a certain degree of error in the calculation of sliding distance, particularly in regions affected by wrinkling, where the fabric undergoes higher levels of in-plane shear. Finally, as indicated in the pure compaction experiments, even under identical experimental conditions, the grease shape exhibited in repeated trials is not entirely consistent. This is attributed to the uneven surface of the NCF material, where the irregularities caused by stitching and fabric tows affect the flow of the grease. Although this influence is not severe, it nevertheless leads to instability in the results when the sliding distances are small.

Although the above analysis highlights certain limitations of the current experimental method, it remains highly effective in tracking large interply sliding. The simulation model employed at this stage has not yet undergone specific validation or optimisation concerning sliding behaviour. As such, the discrepancies currently observed between experimental and simulation results are primarily attributed to shortcomings in the simulation model. In future work, the experimental results obtained in this study will be used to refine the simulation model to achieve more accurate predictive capability.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the development of an experimental system, together with a methodology for tracking inter-ply sliding during forming. The experimental rig incorporates an interchangeable tooling design, enabling flexible investigation of various tool geometries and their influence on fabric deformation. Building upon the established diaphragm forming experimental procedure, a method using grease marks was developed to track interply sliding at designated locations. When the initial weight and geometry of the grease marks are controlled, identical marks exhibit comparable elongation lengths under equivalent sliding distances, with only minor variations. By calibrating the relationship between grease elongation and sliding distance through an overlap test, both the magnitude and direction of inter-ply sliding can be calculated from the deformed shape of the grease marks.

A series of SDF experiments with different tools have been conducted using the sliding tracking method, while the results were compared with finite element simulation results. Based on the comparison results, an analysis was conducted regarding the applicability, effectiveness, and associated errors of the current method. The method has been validated to be effective for tracking the long sliding distance of more than 5 mm. The sliding tracking methodology has shown its potential in simulation model validation and modification. With certain optimisation, this method can be extended

to DDF experiments and even further applied to other studies involving relative interply motion of fabric materials.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is funded by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council, via an EPSRC Doctoral Training Partnership (DTP) studentship and grant number EP/P006701/1, as part of the EPSRC Future Composites Manufacturing Research Hub. The trip to present at ICCM 24 is supported by the Jost Foundation via the Peter Jost Travel Fund.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Krebs, K. Friedrich, and D. Bhattacharyya, "A direct comparison of matched-die versus diaphragm forming," (in English), *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 183-188, 1998/01/01/ 1998, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X\(97\)82706-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X(97)82706-6).
- [2] A. Schnabel and T. Gries, "1 - Production of non-crimp fabrics for composites," in *Non-Crimp Fabric Composites*, S. V. Lomov Ed.: Woodhead Publishing, 2011, pp. 3-41.
- [3] S. Lomov, "Introduction," in *Non-Crimp Fabric Composites*, S. V. Lomov Ed.: Woodhead Publishing, 2011, pp. xvi-xix.
- [4] J. V. Viisainen, A. Hosseini, and M. P. F. Sutcliffe, "Experimental investigation, using 3D digital image correlation, into the effect of component geometry on the wrinkling behaviour and the wrinkling mechanisms of a biaxial NCF during preforming," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 142, p. 106248, 2021/03/01/ 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2020.106248>.
- [5] G. D. Lawrence, S. Chen, N. A. Warrior, and L. T. Harper, "The influence of inter-ply friction during double-diaphragm forming of biaxial NCFs," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 167, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2023.107426.
- [6] F. Yu, S. Chen, L. T. Harper, and N. A. Warrior, "Investigation into the effects of inter-ply sliding during double diaphragm forming for multi-layered biaxial non-crimp fabrics," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 150, p. 106611, 2021/11/01/ 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2021.106611>.
- [7] F. Yu, S. Chen, J. V. Viisainen, M. P. F. Sutcliffe, L. T. Harper, and N. A. Warrior, "A macroscale finite element approach for simulating the bending behaviour of biaxial fabrics," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 191, p. 108078, 2020/05/03/ 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2020.108078>.
- [8] J. P. H. Belnoue and S. R. Hallett, "A rapid multi-scale design tool for the prediction of wrinkle defect formation in composite components," (in English), *Mater Design*, vol. 187, p. 108388, 2020/02/01/ 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2019.108388>.
- [9] W. Huang *et al.*, "A Fourier based reduced model for wrinkling analysis of circular membranes," (in English), *Comput Method Appl M*, vol. 345, pp. 1114-1137, 2019/03/01/ 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2018.09.012>.
- [10] F. Yu, S. Chen, L. T. Harper, and N. A. Warrior, "Simulating the effect of fabric bending stiffness on the wrinkling behaviour of biaxial fabrics during preforming," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 143, p. 106308, 2021/04/01/ 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2021.106308>.
- [11] F. Yu, "The prediction of wrinkle formation in non-crimp fabrics during double diaphragm forming," University of Nottingham, 2022.